

Title: Vanuatu Literacy, Language and Teacher Training Survey
Project: Sustainable Endangered Language Maintenance in the South Pacific
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This document is the literacy, language and teacher training survey that was conducted with schools from the Merei, North Ambrym and Vatlongos language communities in Vanuatu in June/July 2023. The survey was conducted as part of the project on Sustainable Endangered Language Maintenance in the South Pacific, funded by the University of Surrey's Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) Impact Acceleration Account.

The Survey is in English (p2) and Bislama (p10).

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Literacy, Language and Teacher Training survey.

Information about the survey

We are interested in gathering information about language use, ability, and teaching resources in your school. Each survey should take no longer than 15 minutes to complete. We would like the headteacher to fill out all sections (1, 2, 3 & 4). We would like each teacher to fill out sections 2, 3 & 4 only. The headteacher can interview the teachers, or the teachers can fill the survey out on their own. The information will be used to write a policy report for the Curriculum Development Unit. We hope this report will help support you with using and teaching the language in your school.

Teacher's name:

Please send this questionnaire back to Michael Franjeh m.franjeh@surrey.ac.uk

Section 1: Your school

In this section we would like to collect some information about your school.

1. Name of school and the village it is in:

2. Main community language(s) spoken where the school is:

3. Is this a French or English medium school?

4. Number of students in school or kindergarten:

Kindergarten:

Year 1:

Year 2:

Year 3:

Year 4:

Year 5:

Year 6:

Section 2: Teachers

5. What class do you teach?

Kindergarten

Year 1

Year 2

Year 3

Year 4

Year 5

Year 6

For the following questions we ask you to rate how easy or hard it is for you using different parts of the main community language. This is on a scale from 1-5, 1 being hard and 5 being easy. Please circle/highlight the number and we ask you for each question to expand on why you chose this rating.

6. Speaking in the main community language in conversation:

1

2

3

4

5

hard

quite easy

easy

Please explain your rating:

7. Reading in the main community language:

1

2

3

4

5

hard

quite easy

easy

Please explain your rating:

8. Writing in the main community language:

1

2

3

4

5

hard

quite easy

easy

Please explain your rating:

For the following questions we ask you to rate how easy or hard it is for you to use the main community language to teach lessons. This is on a scale from 1-5, 1 being hard and 5 being easy. Please circle/highlight the number and we ask you for each question to expand on why you chose this rating.

9. Speaking the main language to teach lessons:

1 2 3 4 5
hard quite easy easy

Please explain your rating:

10. Reading the main language to teach lessons:

1 2 3 4 5
hard quite easy easy

Please explain your rating:

11. Writing the main language to teach lessons:

1 2 3 4 5
hard quite easy easy

Please explain your rating:

12. What aspects of the language do you find hard and would require more training to effectively teach in the main community language? Please select from the following options (circle/highlight all that apply).

- a. Speaking
- b. Reading
- c. Writing
- d. Other (please specify):

What type/s of training do you require?

13. Which language do you use the most in the classroom? And which language do you use the least? Use numbers 1-3, with 1 being the greatest amount of use, and 3 being the least:

Main community language:

Bislama:

English / French:

14. What do you use the main community language for in the classroom? For example, *written instructions, spoken instructions, explaining difficult things*:

15. Please rate to what extent you like teaching using the main community language, 1 being don't like at all and 5 being really like. Please circle/highlight the number and we ask you to expand on why you chose this rating.

1

2

3

4

5

Don't like at all

Somewhat

Really like

Please explain your rating:

16. Please rate to what extent you think teaching lessons using the main community language helps achieve good educational outcomes for students, 1 being 'not at all' and 5 being 'a lot'. Please circle/highlight the number and we ask you to expand on why you chose this rating.

1 2 3 4 5
Not at all a little a lot

Please explain your rating and explain what the positive benefits or negatives are about education in the main community language:

Section 3: Children

17. Please tell us the total number of children in your class that speak the language:

18. Please tell us the total number of children in your class that do not speak the language:

19. Please explain the reasons why some children do not speak the main community language in your class:

20. Please rate to what extent the children enjoy learning in language, 1 being 'don't enjoy at all' and 5 being 'really enjoy'. Please circle/ highlight the number and we ask you to expand on why you chose this rating.

1 2 3 4 5
Don't enjoy at all Somewhat Really enjoy

Please explain your rating:

21. What aspects do the children find easy when being taught in the main community?
(Circle/highlight all that apply)

- a. Speaking
- b. Reading
- c. Writing
- d. Other (please specify):

22. Please explain why you think the children find these aspects of the language easy:

23. What aspects do the children find hard when learning the language? (Circle/highlight all that apply)

- a. Speaking
- b. Reading
- c. Writing
- d. Other (please specify):

Please explain why you think the children find these aspects of the language difficult:

Section 4: Resources

24. Please list any resources you have to teach language:

25. Do you have access to the Ministry of Education and Training (MoET) materials in your community language: (Circle/highlight answer)

Yes

No

Anything else you would like to mention in relation to this question:

26. If yes, you are using these resources, please explain if the resources are good or there is a need to improve them.

27. Do you make your own language materials: (circle/highlight answer)

Yes

No

28. If yes, what materials have you made?

29. Please list all the different types of resources that you will need to teach the community language in class:

Thank you for completing this survey, please send the completed form back to m.franjeh@surrey.ac.uk

Literasi, Lanwis mo Tija Trening

Infomesen long ol kwestin

Mifala i wantem save kolektem sam infomesen longsaed blong men lanwis blong komuniti (vernacular) long skul mo ol risos blong tijim men lanwis blong komuniti. Ol kwestin i tekem 15 minit blong kompletem. Mifala i askem ol hedtija blong fulumap evri seksen (1, 2, 3 & 4). Mifala i wantem ol tija blong fulumap seksen 2, 3 & 4 nomo. Ol hedtija i save mekem wan interview wetem ol tija blong fulumap seksen 2, 3 & 4, o ol tija oli save fulumap hemwan nomo.

Ol infomesen we mifala i kolektem, bae mifala i raetem wan ripot i go long Curriculum Development Unit long Ministry blong Education mo Training. Mifala i hop se ripot ia bae i givhan blong sapotem skul blong yu taem we yu stap tijim ol lesen long men lanwis blong komuniti.

Nem blong tija:

Plis yu sendem ol kwestin ia i kambak long Michael Franjeh long m.franjeh@surrey.ac.uk

Seksen 1: Skul blong yu

Long seksen ia mifala i wantem save sam infomesen long skul blong yu

1. Nem blong skul mo velej we skul i stap long:

2. Men lanwis blong komuniti we skul i stap long hem:

3. Skul ia hemi Franis o Englis?

4. Namba blong ol student we I stap long skul o kindergarten:

Kindergarten:

Yia 1:

Yia 2:

Yia 3:

Yia 4:

Yia 5:

Yia 6:

Seksen 2: Tija

5. Yu tijim wanem klas?

Kindergarten	Yia 1	Yia 2	Yia 3	Yia 4	Yia 5	Yia 6
<input type="checkbox"/>						

Long ol kwestin ia mifala i askem yu blong tingbaot sapos i isi o had blong yusum ol difren pat blong men lanwis blong komuniti. Mifala i yusum wan skel from 1-5, 1 i minim se i had, mo 5 i minim i isi. Plis haelaetem namba mo eksplenem from wanem yu jusum namba ia.

6. Toktok men lanwis blong komuniti long konvesesen

1	2	3	4	5
had		isi smol		isi

Plis eksplenem tingting:

7. Ridim men lanwis blong komuniti:

1	2	3	4	5
had		isi smol		isi

Plis eksplenem tingting:

8. Raetem men lanwis blong komuniti:

1	2	3	4	5
had		isi smol		isi

Plis eksplenem tingting:

Long ol kwestin ia mifala i askem yu blong tingbaot sapos i isi o had blong yusum men lanwis blong komuniti blong tijim ol lesen. Mifala i yusum wan skel from 1-5, 1 i minim se i had, mo 5 i minim i isi. Plis haelaetem namba mo eksplenem from wanem yu jusum namba ia.

9. Storian long men lanwis blong komuniti blong tijim ol lesen:

1	2	3	4	5
had		isi smol		isi

Plis eksplenem tingting:

10. Rid long men lanwis blong komuniti blong blong tijim ol lesen:

1	2	3	4	5
had		isi smol		isi

Plis eksplenem tingting:

11. Raet long men lanwis blong komuniti blong tijim ol lesen:

1	2	3	4	5
had		isi smol		isi

Plis eksplenem tingting:

12. Wanem pat blong men lanwis blong komuniti we yu faenem i had mo yu ting se yu nidim sam trening blong yusum lanwis long klasrum. Plis haelatem ol pat blong lanwis we yu nidim impruvum.

- e. toktok
- f. ridim
- g. raetem

h. narafala tingting (raetem long bokis):

Plis eksplenem wanem kaen trening yu nidim:

13. Wanem lanwis yu yusum fulap long klasrum blong tijim ol lesen? Mo wijwan yu no yusum fulap? Yusum ol namba 1-3 blong skelem, we 3 i minim 'fulap', mo 1 i minim yu 'no yusum fulap':

Long men lanwis blong komuniti:

Long Bislama:

Long Inglis / Franis:

14. Yu yusum men lanwis blong komuniti long klasrum blong mekem wanem? Olsem yu yusum blong raetem ol instruksen, blong talamaot ol instruksen, o blong eksplenem samting we i had blong andastanem? O wan narafala samting?:

15. Plis skelem hamas yu laekem tij long men lanwis blong komuniti. 1 i minim yu no laekem nating, 5 i minim yu laekem we yu laekem. Plis haelaetem namba mo eksplenem from wanem yu jusum namba ia.

1

2

3

4

5

No laekem nating

laekem smol

laekem tumas

Plis eksplenem tingting:

16. Yu ting se taem we yu yusum men lanwis blong komuniti blong tijim ol lesen i givhan long pikinini blong impruvem save blong olgeta. 1 i minim 'i no givhan nating' mo 5 i minim 'givhan fulap'. Plis haelaetem namba mo eksplenem from wanem yu jusum namba ia.

1 2 3 4 5
No givhan nating givhan smol givhan fulap

Plis eksplenem tingting mo eksplenem ol positiv mo negative longsaed blong tijim ol lessen wetem men lanwis long komuniti:

Seksen 3: Ol Pikinini

17. Plis talem hamas pikinini long klas blong yu i toktok men lanwis blong komuniti:

18. Plis talem hamas pikinini long klas blong yu i no toktok men lanwis blong komuniti:

19. Plis eksplenem from wanem sam pikinini long klas blong yu i no toktok men lanwis blong komuniti:

20. Plis skelem hamas yu ting se ok pikinini i laekem skul long men lanwis blong komuniti: 1 i minim 'oli no laekem nating', 5 i minim 'oli laekem tumas'. Plis haelaetem namba mo eksplenem from wanem yu jusum namba ia..

1 2 3 4 5
No laekem nating laekem smol laekem tumas

Plis eksplenem tingting:

21. Plis haelaetem ol pat blong men lanwis long we ol pikinini i faenem i isi?

e. toktok

f. ridim

g. raetem

h. narafala samting (plis eksplenem):

22. Plis eksplenem from wanem yu ting se ol pikinini i faenem se ol pat blong lanwis ia i isi?

23. Plis haelaetem ol pat blong men lanwis long we ol pikinini i faenem i had?

e. toktok

f. ridim

g. raetem

h. narafala samting (plis eksplenem):

Plis eksplenem from wanem yu ting se ol pikinini i faenem se ol pat blong lanwis ia i had:

Seksen 4: Ol Risos

24. Plis talemaot ol risos blong skul blong tijim ol lesen long men lanwis blong komuniti:

25. I gat ol risos long skul we Ministri blong Edukesen mo Trening (MoET) i bin mekem? Plis haelaetem:

Yes

No

Plis eksplenem ansa o sapos yu gat wan narafala tingting long saed blong ol risos long lanwis:

26. Sapos yes, yu stap yusum ol risos ia? Mo plis talemaot tingting blong yu sapos yu ting se ol risos I gud o I gat nid blong impruvum ol risos ia.

27. Yu mekem ol risos blong tij long lanwis? Plis haelaetem:

Yes

No

28. Sapos yes, plis eksplenem wanem kaen risos yufala i bin mekem:

29. Plis talemaot ol difren kaen risos we yu ting se yu nidim blong yusum Rral long Klas blong tijim ol lesen:

Tankyu tumas blong kompletem ol kwestin. Plis sendem ol ansa blong yu i kambak long m.franjeh@surrey.ac.uk